

IMPLICIT METHODS FOR TESTING PRODUCT PREFERENCE

EXPLORATORY STUDIES WITH THE AFFECTIVE SIMON TASK

Katrina L. Schoen and Nathan Crilly
University of Cambridge, Engineering Design Centre
kls79@eng.cam.ac.uk, nc266@eng.cam.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Design researchers often use interviews and questionnaires to measure consumer response to products. This practice is despite the inherent limitations of these “explicit” self-report methods. In psychology, “implicit” tests have been developed in an attempt to overcome self-report biases and to obtain a more automatic measure of attitudes. This paper investigates the adaptation of implicit methods to measure product preferences. Two exploratory studies were conducted to (i) establish an acceptable methodology for implicit tests using product images, and (ii) determine whether response to products can produce significant effects in affective Simon experiments. Results indicate that (i) the affective Simon task can be modified to assess product stimuli, and (ii) significant differences in consumer response can be measured within product categories. With further work, implicit tests may become a helpful tool for designers and researchers investigating how users respond to product design variations.

Keywords: product form, consumer testing, implicit methods, approach avoidance test, stimulus-response compatibility

INTRODUCTION

This paper outlines the potential benefits of applying research techniques from experimental psychology to investigate product preference. As such, the paper fits into that stream of design research that has contributed methodological developments for measuring consumer response (e.g., see Desmet, Hekkert, & Jacobs, 2000; Mugge, Govers, &

Schoormans, 2009). However, rather than developing alternative or improved self-report methods, we explore the use of implicit measurement techniques that might replace or supplement explicit measures.

We first describe current product design research and conventional methods for gathering consumer feedback. We then review the distinctive characteristics of implicit testing methods and the methodological variables that must be considered when creating an implicit test for use with products. This overview is followed by a report on the design and implementation of two exploratory studies featuring the affective Simon task. Finally, we reflect on procedural findings and present recommendations for the further exploration of implicit tests in product design research.

CONSUMER RESEARCH IN PRODUCT DESIGN

Understanding how people experience designed products has important implications for design research and design practice. Consequently, there have been many attempts to develop knowledge about the relationship between product designs and the responses they elicit from consumers (for overviews, see Bloch, 1995; Crilly, Moultrie & Clarkson, 2004; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005; Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008). In particular, design researchers in academia and industry are often interested in knowing which consumer groups prefer which products, and which product features contribute to those preferences. These questions are often investigated experimentally, by presenting consumers with a range of products or design variants and measuring subjective responses to these stimuli. This process can offer guidance for what products or design variants might be most preferred and can give

useful clues for further design development (for example, see empirical studies in Bell, Hollbrook, & Solomon, 1991; Nagamachi, 2002; Desmet, Hekkert, & Jacobs, 2007; Mugge, Govers, & Schoormans, 2009; Blijlevens, Carbon, Mugge, & Schoormans, 2012).

LIMITATIONS TO CURRENT RESEARCH METHODS

In much of the current research on product form, consumer response is measured using self-report survey methods, such as questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups. Questionnaire methods are especially popular, and often feature attitude response scales such as the Likert Scale or Semantic Differential Rating, as well as open-ended or multiple-choice questions. Although these “explicit” measures can provide helpful feedback to product designers, they are also subject to a number of limitations. Consumer survey responses may not fully capture reactions to a product or predict future behavior, such as purchasing decisions in the marketplace.

This conflict could occur for a variety of reasons; word choice in questionnaires, for example, may inherently bias the responses (Oskamp, 1977). In some cases, participants might be motivated to answer a questionnaire dishonestly, or in a way that seems most socially acceptable; additionally, participants may attempt to provide answers that they believe most likely to please the researcher (Orne, 1962). On the other hand, even if participants respond to carefully-worded questions as honestly as possible, the survey may not be targeting the same thought processes that a consumer faces in the product use scenario or in the marketplace. There is evidence that actual product-related behavior is affected by more spontaneous or impulsive processes, as consumers are often distracted or pressed for time while consuming goods or making purchasing decisions (Friese, Hofmann, & Wänke, 2009). Additionally, consumer judgments may occur nonconsciously or as a result of subliminal influences, and therefore may not be activated during deliberate response to a research survey (Bargh, 2002).

OVERVIEW OF IMPLICIT METHODS

In the field of experimental psychology, so-called “implicit” or “indirect” testing methods have been

developed as an alternative to traditional questionnaires in measuring attitudes and cognitions (De Houwer, 2006). There are many such testing methods, including the Implicit Association Test (IAT), affective priming task, Approach Avoidance Test (AAT), and affective Simon task. In these tests, participants respond to stimulus items using a keyboard, joystick, microphone, or other input device, and their reaction times are measured. Participants are generally slower to respond to “incompatible” trial conditions (e.g. associating a positive stimulus with a negative word or action) than “compatible” trial conditions (e.g. associating a positive stimulus with a positive word or action). Therefore, by assessing reaction times for various trial conditions, researchers can infer information about participants’ attitudes towards the tested stimuli; in many cases, however, participants may not be aware that reaction times are the variable of interest to the researcher.

Implicit measurement techniques may overcome some of the problematic elements of traditional self-report measures of attitudes. Depending on the task design, participants may be unaware of what is being tested, unaware of the actual attitudes or cognitions being measured, or unable to control outcomes (De Houwer, 2006). Although few measures are truly implicit in the sense of fulfilling all these conditions, there is evidence that participants are less able to consciously control the outcome of implicit measures compared to self-report (De Houwer, 2006). Further, implicit measures may be valuable in assessing spontaneous or automatic attitudes towards stimuli, whereas traditional surveys would target consciously constructed and expressed attitudes. In turn, implicit measures could possess particular predictive value in areas focused on spontaneous behavior (De Houwer, 2006).

The implicit reaction time tasks discussed above are not the only non-self-report methods available to researchers. Other methods include psychophysiological techniques such as eye tracking, brain imaging, heart rate measurement, and voice pitch analysis (for an overview of these methods applied to marketing, see Wang & Minor, 2008). Such methods measure variables that are even more resistant to participant response control than reaction

times. However, they typically require specialized equipment, whereas implicit tests can often be inexpensively administered using standard personal computers.

IMPLICIT METHODS IN CONSUMER RESEARCH

Implicit methods have been applied in psychology for various purposes, ranging from investigation of addictions and phobias to indication of racial bias. However, due to the benefits outlined above, implicit measures may also be useful in interpreting consumer attitudes towards products. As with many real-world situations, consumer judgments and behaviors are often subject to nonconscious and automatic influences (Bargh, 2002). For example, implicit measures may be useful in detecting attitudes affected by the perception of a product's prototypical user; this effect is not typically seen in explicit measures (for a discussion of user prototypes and collective self-esteem, see Dimofte, 2010). Moreover, consumers may hold ambivalent attitudes towards products, and implicit methods could be used to predict behavior in those cases (Maison, Greenwald, & Bruin, 2001).

Although implicit techniques seem to have potential application in measuring consumer preferences for different product designs, so far their application in consumer research has been limited to tests focused on brand effects. In an experiment using logos and words to represent Mac and PC, Brunel & Greenwald (2004) used the Implicit Association Test (IAT) to measure significant effects for brand attitude and brand relationship strength, and also found that IAT scores correlated with explicit measures of these constructs; in a second test with advertisements featuring athletes of differing ethnicities, the IAT displayed consumer attitudes that were not detected by explicit measures. Another study found IAT effects indicating consumer preference for brands of yogurt, fast food restaurants, and soft drinks, as well as evidence that the IAT increased the accuracy of predicted behavior compared to explicit measurement only (Maison, Greenwald, & Bruin, 2004). This previous success with the IAT and consumers provides promising evidence that implicit tests could be used to assess product form, as well.

IMPLICIT METHODS FOR PRODUCTS

SELECTING A TESTING METHOD

The field of experimental psychology has developed a large number of implicit testing methods and techniques, many of which could be adapted to study products (for an overview of various test types, see De Houwer, 2003). One important factor that influences the selection and adaptation of an appropriate testing method is the requirement to display images of products rather than verbal stimuli; as in traditional consumer research studies, pictures of various product forms would make up the stimuli under investigation. With this in mind, possible candidates include the IAT, affective priming task, and various forms of approach-avoidance tasks.

To perform the IAT, participants independently categorize items based on either a target concept (such as good/bad) or attribute dimension (such as male/female), followed by combined phases in which the target concepts and attribute dimensions are paired and mapped to key press responses (Greenwald, McGhee, & Schwartz, 1998). The IAT delivers a relatively large effect size, as well as satisfactory reliability and predictive validity (Friese, Hofmann, & Wänke, 2006; Nosek, Greenwald, & Banaji, 2007; Greenwald, et al., 2009). These benefits come with certain constraints, however: stimuli must fall into one of two identifiable categories, and assessments occur at the category level rather than for individual exemplars or stimuli (Brunel & Greenwald, 2004). (Variations of the IAT have been developed to address some of these constraints, including the Single-Category IAT and Go/no-go IAT.) It has been noted that due to the sorting tasks that make up the test, participants may become aware of what is being assessed during the IAT, thereby decreasing the extent to which the method can be considered implicit in that sense (De Houwer, 2003; Roefs et al., 2011).

In affective priming, an initial "prime" stimulus is followed by a "target" stimulus that the participant must categorize by valence (Fazio et al., 1986; Hermans, De Houwer, & Eelen, 1994). The affective priming effect could be utilized in product research by presenting images of products as the prime stimuli,

followed by normatively positive and negative target stimuli (such as the words “good” and “bad”). Advantageously, this measure would assess associations at the individual stimulus level and not for relative categories (Brunel & Greenwald, 2004). However, affective priming has exhibited low internal consistency and reliability compared to other implicit measures (Roefs et al., 2011).

The Approach Avoidance Test has been shown to relate positive and negative evaluations with a predisposition to approach or avoid the stimulus, respectively (Chen & Bargh, 1999). While variants of this method frequently utilize a joystick and zooming images to reinforce the participant’s impression of approaching and avoiding the stimulus, a keystroke manikin version of the affective Simon task (described below) has also been used to display a similar approach-avoidance phenomenon (De Houwer et al., 2001; Rinck & Becker, 2007). Like affective priming, the affective Simon should measure global attitudes towards a specific stimulus item, rather than a specific feature or categorization of the stimulus (De Houwer, 2003). Moreover, unlike the IAT and affective priming task, applying the manikin affective Simon in product research would not require the use of additional words to define categorizing tasks. This setup helps limit the extent to which participants are aware of what is being tested, thus increasing the implicitness of the method; further, the lack of text could facilitate international studies.

ADAPTING THE MANIKIN AFFECTIVE SIMON TASK

Due to the potential adaptation for including images as stimuli, combined with the increased likelihood that participants may not realize what is being tested, we chose to further investigate the possibility of using the manikin affective Simon task in product testing. The task has previously been used to show significant effects for normatively valenced stimuli and food-related stimuli (De Houwer et al., 2001; Laane, 2011); additionally, other approach-avoidance tasks have been used frequently to study forms of addiction and phobia (see Rinck & Becker, 2007; Cousijn, Goudriaan, & Wiers, 2010; Wiers et al., 2010). However, most implicit testing done with consumers has employed the IAT rather than approach-avoidance tasks.

To investigate the use of the affective Simon task for consumer products, we devised two exploratory studies. The primary aim of these studies was not to measure a particular Simon effect of interest (i.e. to answer a question about product preference), but to identify the methodological concerns relevant to this type of test, and to determine whether the affective Simon can become a useful tool for future product research.

Task Design

To participants, the manikin version of the affective Simon task takes the form of a simple computer game. Participants press keys to control the position of a matchstick man character (the “manikin”) on the screen. In each trial, first the manikin appears, and then a stimulus appears; participants must move the manikin towards or away from the stimulus based on a non-affective stimulus feature such as screen location or font color. Over the course of the experiment, this process is repeated many times with the manikin located randomly on either the left or right of the stimulus.

To the experimenter, the assumption is that participants self-identify with the manikin throughout the course of the “game.” In this way, moving towards the stimulus is associated with approach or positive valence; moving away is associated with avoidance or negative valence (De Houwer et al., 2001; Laane, 2011). Moreover, approaching positive stimuli and avoiding negative stimuli creates a compatible condition, while the opposite arrangement (approaching negative stimuli and avoiding positive stimuli) creates an incompatible condition. Participants have been shown to respond faster to the compatible condition than the incompatible condition, indicating that stimulus valence biases the decision to move the manikin towards or away (De Houwer et al., 2001).

In order for an implicit test to be considered a Simon task, it must contain the following features: (i) a “relevant” feature that defines the correct response; (ii) an “irrelevant” feature that the participant must ignore (or may not be fully aware of); and (iii) possible responses that relate to the irrelevant feature only (De Houwer et al., 2001). Further, in an affective version of the Simon paradigm, stimulus valence serves as

the irrelevant feature; this valence is related to the responses because both possess affective properties (De Houwer, 1998). For our study of product designs, therefore, stimulus assessment serves as both the “irrelevant” feature and the variable of interest inferred from measured reaction time results.

As in previous manikin designs (De Houwer et al., 2001; Laane, 2011), the affective responses used here were key presses to move towards or away from the stimulus images. During experiments, a key on the far left ('z') and a key on the far right ('/') of the keyboard were labeled with stickers depicting left and right arrows, respectively.

In previous manikin experiments that used vocabulary words as stimuli, the relevant feature was grammatical category (adjectives vs. nouns) or typography (uppercase vs. lowercase) (De Houwer et al., 2001; Laane, 2011). With images as stimuli, another relevant feature must be manipulated; in order to maintain the integrity of the test, however, altering this feature should not be meaningfully related to the correct response. For the first experimental study, spatial location on the screen was chosen as the relevant feature for product images. Specifically, each image was presented approximately 1 centimeter above or below the horizontal centerline. Depending on its location (above or below center), participants were instructed to make the manikin move towards or away from the image. The stimulus image was always presented on the vertical centerline of the screen, but the manikin could appear to the left or right of the image. Figure 1 provides screenshots of a potential trial for this affective Simon Task design.

Figure 1. Cropped screenshots from the affective Simon task: (upper image) the stimulus appears above center; (lower image) as a response, the participant moves the manikin towards the stimulus

Stimulus Selection

A primary concern was the selection of product stimuli to be presented in the affective Simon test. For the exploratory studies, stimuli were selected based on their likelihood of showing a substantial affective Simon effect. Cell phones were initially chosen, due to their near-universal usage, a high level of user involvement, and the number of product options available. In order to represent a variety of phone styles and brands, the four selected products were as follows: Samsung Galaxy S, Apple iPhone 4, Motorola i365, and LG C2000 (Figure 2). We expected that approach bias would be significantly greater for the two newer smartphones compared to the two older and less prestigious models. Images used for experimentation provide a front view of each phone, with a plain white background. Images were normalized to a height of 326 pixels.

Figure 2. Phone stimuli, from left to right: (1) Samsung Galaxy S, (2) Motorola i365, (3) Apple iPhone 4, (4) LG C2000

In addition to product images, further stimuli were used for comparison of results. Two male and two female faces were generated using the interactive demos provided by Face Research (2012) (Figure 3). For each gender, a relatively “attractive” face was created by taking the average of ten faces, while a single image of those ten served as an unmodified “individual” (see Langlois & Roggman, 1990; Tiddeman, Burt, & Perrett, 2001). We expected that approach bias would be significantly greater for the averaged faces compared to individual faces. Face images were 272 x 362 pixels.

Figure 3. Face stimuli, from left to right: (1) averaged female, (2) individual female, (3) averaged male, (4) individual male. Images courtesy of Face Research (2012)

Finally, four geometric shapes (triangle, square, pentagon, hexagon) were used as the third category of stimuli (Figure 4). We expected that approach bias values would not be significantly different for any of the shapes. Shape images had maximum dimensions of 220 x 220 pixels.

Figure 4. Shape stimuli, from left to right: (1) triangle, (2) square, (3) pentagon, (4) hexagon

EXPLORATORY STUDY 1

APPARATUS

All experiments were completed on a MacBook Pro 15-inch laptop computer running Mac OS X 10.4.11, with screen resolution 1440 x 900. Experiments were created and presented to participants using SuperLab software (Cedrus Corporation, 2006), which also recorded reaction times.

PARTICIPANTS

Twelve male students/researchers at the University of Cambridge volunteered to participate in the experiment. Although not necessarily representative of the broader population, this participant sample is adequate for the purposes of methodological development. Compared to the overall consumer population, this group also offers the advantage of limited variation in age, sensory and physical ability, socio-economic status, and educational achievement. For this preliminary investigation of experimental procedures, this sample consistency may help to reduce the effects of confounding variables and eliminate certain issues, such as discomfort with a computerized testing environment.

PROCEDURE

Participants were seated in front of the laptop computer and given a standard verbal description of the task. They were then presented with on-screen directions and an opportunity to ask the experimenter any questions, after which they proceeded to a practice block. They completed three experimental blocks, with one block for each stimulus category (faces, phones, products); the blocks were then

repeated in the same order. Block order and instruction condition (location above/below the centerline relating to moving towards/away) were counterbalanced between subjects. Self-timed breaks were provided between blocks. Following the affective Simon experiment, participants filled out a paper-and-pencil questionnaire that featured the same printed images accompanied by the question "How attractive is this {face/product/shape} to you?" and a portrait version of the 9-point affective Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) scale (Lang, 1980; Irtel, 2007). Participants were debriefed as to the purpose of the experiment and allowed to comment on their experience or ask any further questions. The entire procedure took approximately 15 minutes per person.

Practice blocks consisted of twelve trials. In the experimental blocks, the four initial trials were systematically discarded due to generally lengthened response times at the start of each block (Greenwald, 1998). The 16 measured trials followed, such that each of the four stimuli appeared in all four possible configurations: above and below center, with the manikin on the left and right side of the screen. This condition accounted for right- or left-hand dominance and potentially faster reaction times on one arrow key versus the other. The order of trial presentation was randomized in SuperLab. Over the six blocks, there was a total of 96 experimental trials per participant.

A single trial of the experiment proceeded as follows. The manikin figure appeared on either the left or right side of the screen for 750 ms. A stimulus image then appeared either above or below center on the screen, at which point the participant responded with the appropriate key press. For a correct response, the manikin moved towards or away from the stimulus image, simulated with a series of images moving 200 pixels to the left or right over a period of 60 ms and staying at the final position for a further 100 ms, after which the screen was cleared. For an incorrect response, a red "X" appeared in the center of the screen for 300 ms, after which the screen was cleared. The inter-trial interval was 1500 ms. (Event sequence and timing for the tasks were based on Laane, 2011).

STATISTICAL METHODS

Data was imported into Matlab (The MathWorks, Inc., 2008) and SPSS (IBM Corporation, 2009) for analysis. Reaction times were not included for trials where an incorrect response was given, except to compute the percentage of incorrect responses. In order to eliminate extreme values in the data, which are generally taken to indicate anticipations or inattention, values outside the 150 ms – 1500 ms range were recoded to 150 ms or 1500 ms (Laane, 2011). Data was recoded rather than removed due to the small number of trials; further, the recoding method is insensitive to the proportion of outliers that lie in the upper end of the distribution versus the lower end (Greenwald, 1998).

Reaction time data was log-transformed to ensure satisfactory stability of variance for statistical analysis and to mitigate the dependence of effect size on overall reaction time for the specific task being performed (Greenwald, 1998; De Houwer et al., 2001). “Approach bias” values were calculated for each stimulus for each participant, where approach bias is defined as (log) average avoidance reaction time minus (log) average approach reaction time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total average reaction time for the test was 698 ms, and 4.08% of total responses were incorrect. The correlation between incorrect responses and reaction time was positive and insignificant ($r = 0.04$, $p = 0.49$).

Reaction Times

Mean reaction times (untransformed) for the twelve stimuli are summarized in Figure 5. For all stimuli except one (Shape #2, the square), reaction times were shorter for the approach condition than the avoidance condition. A two-tailed, one-sample t-test also revealed that mean approach bias values were significantly greater than zero for all three stimulus categories: faces, $t(11) = 2.66$, $p = 0.02$; phones, $t(11) = 3.32$, $p < 0.01$; and shapes, $t(11) = 3.21$, $p < 0.01$. This strong pattern of positive approach bias could indicate a potential problem with the task design.

Figure 5. Mean approach and avoidance times for stimuli in Study 1: faces (upper image), phones (middle image), and shapes (lower image)

A repeated measures ANOVA was performed to compare the approach bias values for various sets of stimuli. The ANOVA did not reveal that the approach bias for averaged faces differed significantly from that of individual faces, nor that the approach bias for older phones differed significantly from that of newer phones. Pairwise comparisons (using Bonferroni's correction for multiple comparisons) did not reveal significant differences in approach bias between individual stimuli within each category.

Correlations

Correlation coefficients were computed between the implicit and explicit scores. The implicit score is a participant's approach bias value for a particular stimulus; the corresponding explicit score is the affective SAM rating reported by the same participant for the same stimulus. Correlation coefficient values are presented in Table 1; p -values are shown in parentheses next to each coefficient. There was a positive overall correlation between implicit and explicit scores. For each category computed

individually, the correlation was negative for faces and shapes but positive for phones. None of the regression coefficients were statistically significant.

Category	Correlation coefficient
All stimuli	0.01 (0.86)
Faces	-0.07 (0.61)
Phones	0.12 (0.42)
Shapes	-0.05 (0.71)

Table 1. Correlation coefficients between implicit and explicit measures, Study 1

EXPLORATORY STUDY 2

STIMULUS AND TASK ALTERATIONS

Following Study 1, we decided to design a second experiment that would improve upon certain aspects of the procedure and test different task conditions. In particular, we wanted to: (i) apply the affective Simon task with another category of products, (ii) alter the relevant task condition and timing of trial presentations, and (iii) use an onscreen questionnaire rather than the paper-and-pencil version, to provide consistency of image presentation between the implicit and explicit measures.

Cell phone images were replaced with cars in order to develop the experiment using a second product category. As with phones, vehicles were chosen due to their wide appeal, user involvement, and variety of models for potential testing. Two sports cars and two utility vehicles were tested: 2011 Porsche Cayman, 2011 BMW Z4, 2010 Nissan Cube, and 2011 Scion xB (Figure 6).

We expected that a greater approach bias would be measured for sports cars compared to utility vehicles. Vehicles were displayed at a standard $\frac{3}{4}$ frontal view, with a plain white background; all models were shown in a silver exterior and black interior coloring. Images were normalized to a height of 254 pixels for sports cars and 326 pixels for utility vehicles to provide a sense of scale. The same four faces were again tested.

Figure 6. Vehicle stimuli, clockwise from top left: 1) Porsche Cayman, 2) Nissan Cube, 3) BMW Z4, 4) Scion xB

Taking into account feedback from participants in Study 1, that the above/below center condition was sometimes difficult to distinguish, Study 2 incorporated a different relevant feature for the Simon task. Instead of appearing above or below center on the screen, images were rotated approximately 10 degrees clockwise or counterclockwise (Cousijn, Goudriaan, & Wiers, 2010). Depending on the direction of rotation, participants were instructed to make the manikin move towards or away from the image.

Additionally, the second study implemented a “fixation period” before introducing the relevant feature in each trial. Images first appeared, without any rotation, in the center of the screen for 2000 ms (two seconds). This step was added to address two issues that arose in the previous study; (i) since the product images are not full rectangular images, but instead show the outline and contours of the item itself, spatial location and rotation can be difficult to perceive without comparison to a visual reference; and (ii) participants could “blur their eyes” to determine spatial location without actually perceiving the image contents. The 2000 ms fixation period was also intended to encourage participants to focus on the stimulus image and to permit visual processing of that stimulus prior to the relevant approach-avoid cue (Reimann et al., 2010). Figure 7 provides screenshots from a potential trial in the revised study design.

Figure 7. Cropped screenshots from the affective Simon task: (upper image) the stimulus appears and stays onscreen for a “focusing period;” (middle image) the stimulus rotates clockwise; (lower image) as a response, the participant moves the manikin away from the stimulus

Finally, the paper-and-pencil SAM questionnaire was replaced with an onscreen version incorporated into the SuperLab generated test. This ensured that product images appeared exactly the same in both implicit and explicit measurement processes.

PARTICIPANTS

Twelve male students/researchers at the University of Cambridge volunteered to participate in the experiment. Participants did not take part in Study 1.

PROCEDURE

As with the first study, participants were seated in front of the laptop computer, given a standard verbal description of the task, presented with on-screen directions, and given an opportunity to ask the experimenter any questions. They completed two experimental blocks, each preceded by a practice block, with one block for each response condition (clockwise/counterclockwise related to moving towards/away); block order was counterbalanced between subjects. Each block contained intermixed vehicle and face stimuli. Self-timed breaks were provided between blocks. Following the affective Simon experiment, participants answered an on-screen questionnaire that featured the tested images, one by one, accompanied by the question “How attractive is this image to you?” and the 9-point portrait affective SAM scale labeled with numbers 1-9. Participants responded to the questionnaire using numbers 1-9 on the top row of the keyboard. Participants were debriefed as in Study 1, and similarly the entire procedure took about 15 minutes per participant.

Practice blocks consisted of 8 trials. Again, 4 initial trials in each experimental block were discarded, followed by 32 measured trials. For both experimental blocks, each of the eight stimuli appeared in all four possible configurations: rotated clockwise and counterclockwise, with the manikin on the left and right side of the screen. The order of trial presentation was randomized in SuperLab. Over the two blocks, there was a total of 64 experimental trials per participant.

A single trial of the experiment proceeded as follows. The manikin figure appeared on either the left or right side of the screen for 750 ms, after which a stimulus image appeared centered on the screen for 2 seconds. The image then tilted either clockwise or counterclockwise, at which point the participant responded with the appropriate key press. Feedback for correct and incorrect responses was identical to Study 1. The inter-trial interval was 1500 ms.

STATISTICAL METHODS

Data analysis proceeded as in Study 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total average reaction time for the test was 820 ms, longer than in Study 1. 4.82% of total responses were incorrect, slightly more than in Study 1. The correlation between error rate and response time was negative and insignificant ($r = -0.03$, $p = 0.71$). Normally in implicit testing results of this type, error rates and reaction times follow the same pattern and are therefore positively correlated (i.e. tasks with slower response times are more likely to be incorrect) (De Houwer et al., 2001). The negative value here, though insignificant, could indicate a problematic test setup or an insufficient amount of data.

Reaction Times

Mean reaction times (untransformed) for the eight stimuli are summarized in Figure 8. Approach times were faster than avoidance times for the two sports cars, while avoidance times were faster than approach times for utility vehicles. This pattern supports our expectation of finding an approach bias for the sports cars compared to utility vehicles.

A two-tailed, one-sample t-test revealed that mean approach bias values were not significantly different from zero for either stimulus category.

Figure 8. Mean approach and avoidance times for stimuli in Study 2: faces (upper image), and vehicles (lower image)

The repeated measures ANOVA revealed that the approach bias for individual faces was significantly greater than that of averaged faces, $F(1,11) = 12.41, p < 0.01$. Additionally, the approach bias for sports cars was significantly greater than for utility vehicles, $F(1,11) = 8.87, p = 0.01$. Pairwise comparisons revealed that approach bias values were not significantly different between the two sports cars (or between the two utility vehicles), providing a sense of the test's sensitivity in distinguishing between particular stimuli.

Correlations

Correlation coefficients were computed between implicit and explicit scores for each stimulus given by each participant. These values are presented in Table 2; *p*-values are shown in parentheses next to each coefficient. The correlation was positive for all categories overall, negative for faces, and positive for vehicles. The correlation coefficient for the vehicle category was marginally significant ($p = 0.07$).

Category	Correlation coefficient
All stimuli	0.11 (0.26)
Faces	-0.03 (0.86)
Vehicles	0.27 (0.07)

Table 2. Correlation coefficients between implicit and explicit measures, Study 2

GENERAL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The two exploratory studies described here provide a useful overview of certain key methodological variables that should be considered when implementing implicit testing for products. Particular challenges worth highlighting include: (i) selection and normalization of product images such that the test measures the comparisons of interest, (ii) definition of relevant features, irrelevant features, and participant responses for a legitimate task design, and (iii) selection of appropriate statistical analysis procedures.

In Study 2, we found a significant difference in approach bias values between sports cars and utility vehicles. However, in Study 1, implicit measures did not support the simple expectation that participants would approach smartphones and avoid older phones. These mixed results might variously be interpreted as indicating that: (i) the affective Simon task measures were highly sensitive to the modifications made to the task procedure between the two studies, (ii) our choice of products or product images was problematic, (iii) our expectations about participants' preferences were incorrect, or (iv) the affective Simon task is measuring a different or more complex construct than product preference alone.

Self-report "attractiveness" scores were strongly correlated with approach bias values for vehicles, but not for any other stimulus categories. While comparing implicit measures to other data sources may be informative, implicit and explicit measures may converge in some cases and diverge in others. Even when the two measurements are positively correlated, implicit testing may provide information beyond what is attainable through traditional survey methods. Implicit methods are only useful if they provide data that differs from self-report, but such

differences also lead to difficulty in interpreting implicit test results.

The inclusion of shapes and faces provided an interesting comparison to the product stimuli. Following the explicit questionnaire, more than one participant expressed difficulty or amusement at being asked to explicitly evaluate the attractiveness of certain stimuli, particularly geometric shapes and faces of their own gender; in this way, implicit methods could provide feedback in areas where participants have some trouble explicitly stating their preferences. Further, whereas it seems difficult for people to deliberately evaluate very different stimuli using a single explicit criterion, implicit tests may provide an enhanced measure for cross-category comparison.

In these experimental studies, we selected products from two categories (phone models and car models) with the intention of measuring significant differences in approach bias among product stimuli. If the method could be refined to measure attitudes with sufficient sensitivity, variants of particular designs could also be used as stimuli, offering feedback on the viability of different design directions.

In the ongoing work to adapt these testing procedures for design research, it will be helpful to add multiple explicit questions to the self-report stage. Instead of a single "attractiveness" rating, we might ask about "liking" or "wanting," or employ additional methods such as the Semantic Differential Scale or nonverbal self-report instruments. Comparison with some real-world measure such as willingness to pay, prior ownership, or observed consumption behavior may also be instructive. The added data from these measures will provide an enhanced view of comparisons and correlations between implicit and explicit measures. It may also be worthwhile to test a version of the manikin task where the correct response is determined by a feature such as class membership (product color, shape, brand, etc.), instead of image location or rotation; the test would then structurally mimic other approach-avoidance methods rather than the affective Simon task (Rinck & Becker, 2007). Additionally, data could be analyzed on the participant level rather than in aggregate, to

reflect individual attitudes. Once exploratory testing is concluded, larger sample sizes may help to establish test reliability and show stronger effects. Focus can then shift from methodological concerns about the implementation and validity of the affective Simon task to actual implementation of the test to answer research questions about product preference.

Although future experimentation is necessary to establish implicit testing as a tool for design research, the studies and results presented here contribute to the development of such methodology and provide evidence that significant implicit effects can be obtained for products. We suggest that further development of implicit methods for design research has the potential to widen the methods available for measuring product preference. Implicit testing could then be implemented either individually or in combination with self-report measures. In combination, they might be used to test the validity of self-report results, to offer methodological triangulation or simply to provide a different perspective. As such, implicit methods might contribute to developing a better understanding of how people experience design and offer a useful tool for design research and design practice.

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